

GENDER-RELATED DIFFERENCES IN THE PREVALENCE OF TETRALOGY OF FALLOT IN YOUNG CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Tetralogy of Fallot (TOF) is one of the most common cyanotic congenital heart defects in children and requires early surgical intervention. In recent years, cardiac biomarkers have increasingly been considered as potential predictors of clinical outcomes in patients with Tetralogy of Fallot. However, sex-related differences in disease prevalence and the possible prognostic significance of biomarkers remain insufficiently studied to date.

Introduction

Tetralogy of Fallot (TOF) is one of the most common cyanotic congenital heart defects in children and requires early surgical intervention. In recent years, cardiac biomarkers have increasingly been considered as potential predictors of clinical outcomes in patients with Tetralogy of Fallot. However, sex-related differences in disease prevalence and the possible prognostic significance of biomarkers remain insufficiently studied to date.

Aim of the Study

To determine the characteristics of gender distribution among young children diagnosed with Tetralogy of Fallot.

Materials and Methods

A clinical cohort of 32 patients with a verified diagnosis of Tetralogy of Fallot was formed at the National Children's Medical Center. The age of the children ranged from 0 to 2 years. Of these patients, 29 (90.6%) were boys and 3 (9.4%) were girls, corresponding to a male-to-female ratio of 9.7:1.

Conclusion

The analysis of gender distribution in the studied cohort of patients with Tetralogy of Fallot revealed a marked predominance of males, with a ratio of 9.7:1. This finding suggests the possible presence of sex-related differences in the prevalence of this congenital heart defect. Potential pathogenetic mechanisms may include sex-linked genetic factors, differences in hormonal regulation during embryonic cardiogenesis, as well as epigenetic features influencing the formation of the fetal cardiovascular system.

References:

1. AKZAMOVNA, Z. R., XABIBULLAYEVNA, S. B., KAMARDINOVNA, N. D., & TOXTABAYEVICH, B. Q. (2019). THE STUDY OF THE POLYMORPHIC GENE AGTR1 1166 A> C AND A MARKER OF

NEPHRINE WITH DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 1 DIABETES IN THE UZBEK POPULATION. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research (09752366), 11(3).

2. Шагазатова, Б. Х., & Рахимбердиева, З. А. (2024). РАННИЕ БИОМАРКЕРЫ ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ ПОЧЕК. Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences, 4(9), 34-44.

3. Нажмутдинова, Д. К., Рахимбердиева, З. А., & Максудова, Д. Р. (2017). Relationship of autoimmune thyroids with violations of reproductive function in women of childbearing age. Евразийский Союз Ученых, (2 (35)), 31-34.

4. Рахимбердиева, З. А., & Артикова, Д. М. (2020). Шагазатова Барно Хабибуллаевна. EDITOR COORDINATOR, 468.

